

THE RANKING OF AESTHETIC MOBILE LEARNING INTERFACES BASED ON EXPERTS’ EVALUATION FOR HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Mobile learning (m-learning) refers to the use of mobile devices in the learning process. These devices help overcome the boundaries of time, space, and location. The aesthetic interface of m-learning applications is one of the important factors in engaging students during learning sessions. However, the increasing use of mobile applications in educational settings has been associated with higher levels of student disengagement. In addition, m-learning applications continue to face challenges such as inadequate aesthetic interfaces, student disengagement, and low overall usage. Therefore, this study aims to determine the aesthetics of mlearning application interfaces based on expert evaluation. Ten interfaces of an mlearning application, consisting of the Homepage, Introduction Page, and Learning Page, were presented to experts for evaluation. The evaluation data were then analysed and ranked using the Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) technique. The results of the interface ranking showed that Interface H1 was the most aesthetic interface for the Homepage, Interface I1 for the Introduction Page, and Interface L6 for the Learning Page. The findings of the study also revealed that contrast is the most important design principle in determining interface aesthetics.*

Keywords: *Aesthetic, User interface, Mobile learning application, Higher education, Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process.*

1. INTRODUCTION

This study intends to focus on the mobile-based learning interface because of the developing technology and the increased usage of mobile devices. Mobile learning or m-learning is the use of mobile devices in education. The vast usage of mobile devices nowadays and the availability of them promote the success of m-learning as students are no longer held back by the limitations of time or place. [1] stated the sum of smartphone users in Malaysia is predicted to be close to 29 million in 2021. By 2025, Malaysian smartphone users are predicted to climb by 1.74 million with an average of 7.5 hours spend on the internet and 2.45 hours on social media each day. However, [2] stated m-learning applications are facing a common problem of low retention rate that is the percentage of users continuing to use an application within a certain number of days since first use. Meaning there are more application being uninstal after a short usage. The increased use of mobile devices in educational settings has been associated with higher levels of student disengagement [3]. Student disengagement has emerged as a significant issue in e-learning and m-learning [4].

On the other hand, [5] finds that the aesthetics have an important role to play in generating positive emotions to students’ intention to use online education applications (OEs). Aesthetic design significantly decreased participant cognitive load and increased student

satisfaction and willingness to continue usage [6]. Aesthetic refers to the high loading on the whole of impression, beauty and meaningfulness. The aesthetic of interface is crucial since it effect the users' initial impression, attention, satisfaction, subjective experiences and effective communications [7]. The aesthetic of the interface could encourage students to the content of the learning modules and inspire students to further explore the learning materials. Therefore, this study intends to design mobile-learning (mlearning) interface based on the selected aesthetic design principles and further rank the aesthetic of those interfaces using Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) technique.

The remainder of the paper are discussed in the following sections. Section 2 explains the methodology adopted of this study, whereas Section 3 discusses about the results and discussions in this research. Finally, the conclusion is presented in Section 4.

2. METHODOLOGY

There are two (2) basic research approaches: quantitative research and qualitative research. This study adopted quantitative research approach. A quantitative approach is used to investigate and comprehend the meaning that individuals or groups attribute to a social or human problem [8]. A survey is a commonly used method in quantitative research. This study employed a survey to collect the data on aesthetic interface design based on experts' evaluation. Then, the data will analyse using Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) technique for ranking the interfaces. The details of the methodology of this study are explained in the following subsections.

2.1 Participants

There are five (5) experts involved as participants in this study. They have experience in system design and development such as graphic designer, test analyst and others. These experts obtained at least two (2) years of experience. The experts were required to evaluate the design of interfaces regarding to the design principles applied on those interfaces.

2.2 Materials

This study considered three (3) categories of m-learning interfaces which are Homepage, Introduction Page, and Learning Page. In this study, there are two (2) Homepage, two (2) Introduction Page and six (6) Learning page, in which altogether consists of 10 interfaces.

Firstly, the Homepage serves as the main interface when students use the application. It consists of the application name and menu for easy access and acts as the face of the application. Secondly, the Introduction page where information regarding the subject is usually placed. This interface introduced the subject chosen by the student and provided a brief overview of the whole subject. Finally, the Learning page in which, students are expected to view the lesson given on the subject.

Five (5) designs principles are considered in this research which are balance, emphasis, alignment, contrast and consistency. These design principles were determined during a literature review studies. Each interface applied three (3) combinations of design principles as illustrated in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 respectively in Section 3 - Results and Discussion.

2.3 Data Collection

The survey was conducted by the distribution of a booklet containing 10 m-learning interfaces. The participants were required to rate the elements and criteria used in the m-learning interface design on a scale of one (1) to five (5), with 1 as equally important and 5 as very important. Then, the participants are expected to rate the interfaces in relation to the criteria and elements for the step of interface ranking.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data collected from the experts’ evaluation which is 10 m-learning interfaces were ranked using the FAHP technique. During this phase, the weight for the criteria is acquired. The criteria weight will then be used in the process of interface ranking.

These ratings data from the experts are typically provided in the form of fuzzy data. Fuzzy data can include language factors. This phase is intended to turn fuzzy data into triangular fuzzy integers. In the aggregation step, a weight for criterion based on the geometric mean technique is used. In the selection phase, the fuzzy weight of individual attributes and the overall fuzzy scores of individual alternatives are defuzzied during the defuzzification stage. These alternatives are then ranked using crisp Best Non-Fuzzy Performance values (BNP). This study focuses on the rating phase for evaluating criteria. TFN is a fuzzy number represented by three points as follows: $A = (L, M, U)$ [9]. Triangular fuzzy number (TFN) is the most popular one among the various shapes of fuzzy numbers (Trapezoidal fuzzy number, Gaussian fuzzy number and many more).

This technique employs pair-wise comparisons to provide decision-makers with more precise information. Humans use the linguistic environment to make decisions in the real world. The traditional decision-making method only works with exact and ordinary data, not qualitative data. Fuzzy can be used to assess humans in a vague and qualitative manner [10]. This study used linguistic variables to express reasonable situations that are difficult to define. The steps of Buckley (1985) [11] method in the FAHP technique are as follows:

i. Decompose the problem and construct the hierarchy. ii. Convert all linguistic terms to TFNs as in Equation

$$A = \begin{matrix} 1 & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_n & \cdots & 1 \end{matrix} = \begin{matrix} 1 & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & \cdots & 1 \end{matrix} \quad \text{Equation 3.1}$$

a_{12}

where,

$1, 3, 5, 7, 9$

$a_{ij} = \begin{cases} \text{criteria } i \text{ is relative importance to criterion } j & i < j \\ 1, & i = j \\ \text{criteria } i \text{ is relative less importance to criterion } j & i > j \end{cases}$

$1 \ 1, \ 3 \ 1, \ 5 \ 1, \ 7 \ 1, \ 9 \ 1$

iii. Construct the priority weight for the hierarchy structure in fuzzy rating matrix using Equation 3.2.

$$r_i = (a_{i1} \otimes a_{i2} \otimes \dots \otimes a_{in})^{1/n}, w_i = r_i \otimes (r_1 \oplus r_2 \oplus \dots \oplus r_n)^{-1}$$

Equation 3.2

iv. Compute the priority weight for each criterion.
 v. Obtain the priority weight for the sub-criteria and alternatives with respect to each criterion with Equation 3.3.

$$E_{ij} = (1/m) \square E^{1ij} \square E^{2ij} \square \dots \square E^{mij} \quad \text{Equation 3.3}$$

vi. Obtain the priority of overall weights in the entire hierarchy using Geometric Mean (Buckley Method).

$$LR_i = \prod_{j=1}^n UE_{ij} \times LW_j; MR_i = \prod_{j=1}^n ME_{ij} \times Mw_j; UR_i = \prod_{j=1}^n UE_{ij} \times Uw_j$$

Equation 3.4

vii. Determine total scores of individual alternatives using.
 viii. Determine the BNP using the Centre of Area (COA) method (Equation 3.5).
 ix. Rank the best alternatives.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the interface ranking are shown in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 1. Result of Homepage Interfaces Ranking

Interface	Design Principles	Interface Design	
Homepage 1 (H1)	Balance, alignment, consistency		
Homepage 2 (H2)	Balance, emphasis, consistency		

Table 2. Result of Introduction Page Interfaces Ranking

Interface	Design Principles	Interface Design	Rank
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<p>Introduction Page 1 (I1)</p>	<p>Balance, alignment, consistency</p>		<p>1</p>
<p>Introduction Page 2 (I2)</p>	<p>Balance, alignment, emphasis</p>		<p>2</p>

Table 3. Result of Learning Page Interfaces Ranking

Interface	Design Principles	Interface Design	
<p>Learning Page 1 (L1)</p>	<p>Balance, alignment, consistency</p>		<p>2</p>
<p>Learning Page 2 (L2)</p>	<p>Consistency, alignment, emphasis</p>		<p>3</p>

<p>Learning Page 3 (L3)</p>	<p>Contrast, emphasis, balance</p>		<p>6</p>
<p>Learning Page 4 (L4)</p>	<p>Balance, alignment, emphasis</p>		<p>4</p>
<p>Interface</p>	<p>Design Principles</p>	<p>Interface Design</p>	
<p>Learning Page 5 (L5)</p>	<p>Balance, alignment, consistency</p>		<p>5</p>
<p>Learning Page 6 (L6)</p>	<p>Balance, alignment, consistency</p>		<p>1</p>

4. CONCLUSION

The FAHP technique is effective in ranking interface aesthetics. The findings of this study may serve as a guideline for designers in developing mobile learning application interfaces that enhance student engagement during learning sessions

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